

Sustainable Southwest Beef Project

Beef Brief:

ECONOMICS OF RARÁMURI CRIOLLO AND CONVENTIONAL CATTLE PRODUCTION

The Background

Limited forage availability and thin profit margins are major challenges for ranchers of the Southwestern U.S. Most calves from these ranches are shipped to feedlots for finishing on grain. Segments of society are concerned about air and water pollution and animal welfare in the large feedlot systems. Potential options for ranchers dealing with these challenges are the use of alternative cattle genetics, such as Rarámuri Criollo, a heritage biotype brought to the Americas by Spanish Conquistadors, as well as pursuing a marketing strategy with grass-fed, naturally raised, locally produced meats.

We developed a model of a medium-sized ranch in Southern New Mexico (4662 ha; 150 Animal Unit Year or AU) which we consider a typical ranch in the region. We used that typical ranch setting to compare economic outcomes of raising a Rarámuri Criollo (heritage breed) herd finished on rangeland versus an Angus Hereford cross (conventional breed) herd in which calves are shipped for finishing on grain so that the ranch-level economic outcomes could be compared.

Differences in grazing distance from watering points on arid rangeland (Figure 1), rates of gain, production performance, sale prices, production costs, and timing of sale were considered in the budget comparison. More specifically, we calculated the net return to land and risk, which takes into account operating costs (supplemental feed and vet costs) and overhead costs (vehicles, buildings, livestock investment, and labor) to form total costs. Two price scenarios were used, the 2009-2013 mean prices and 2014 prices, a relatively high price year. In each scenario, the heritage enterprise had the same number of cows as the conventional enterprise.

Figure 1. Observed used (color) and unused (white) locations of foraging by Conventional vs. Heritage cattle during the spring and fall seasons.

Results

We found that a ranch with conventional cattle and 150 AU available can support 112 cows. Because of the longer feeding period for heritage cattle, 112 cows would require 226 AU. Comparison of conventional and heritage cattle revenues, total costs and risk-adjusted net annual returns are given for 2009-2013 mean prices (Figure 2) and 2014 prices (Figure 3).

Cost savings with the heritage breed include:

1. Lower supplemental feed costs (about half) because supplements are fed only to steers and lower cost supplements are fed. Even though they are finished on grass. This savings relates to the tendency of the heritage breed to graze farther from water.
2. Lower veterinary and medicine costs due to reduced fly and parasite control.

Figure 2. Comparison of Revenues, Costs, and Net Returns to Land and Risk, Conventional vs. Heritage Cattle, Mean Real Beef Prices (2009 – 2013).

Figure 3. Comparison in Revenues, Costs, and Net Returns to Land and Risk between Conventional vs. Heritage Cattle, 2014 Observed Beef Prices.

Policy Issues:

Perceived problems with conventional U.S. beef production system include air and water pollution, waste management problems, animal welfare issues, and human health concerns associated with confined large-scale feedlots. These concerns have stimulated producer and consumer interest in grass-fed, naturally raised, locally produced meats. Finding cattle breeds that can efficiently finish on grass can be problematic, especially in the arid Southwestern U.S., as most conventional cattle are too large to finish quickly and easily on grass alone. This study suggests that the behavior and characteristics of Rarámuri Criollo cattle provide a promising breed from a financial standpoint for desert ranchers.

For more information please visit southwestbeef.org

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